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GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR THE EDUCATIONAL COMPONENT

PREVQUEDAS_BRASIL RCT

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1. INTRODUCTION

The educational component is one of the main pillars of the Clinical Trial – PREVQUEDAS BRASIL and aims primarily to establish educational measures designed to The educational component is a key pillar of the Clinical Trial – PREVQUEDAS BRASIL, and its primary aim is to implement educational measures that produce lasting changes in habits and behaviours that increase the risk of falls. It also seeks to improve self-efficacy in daily activities by transforming existing knowledge and empowering patients to take responsibility for their health and associated risks. The adopted educational model is based on individuals' knowledge (habits, roles, living conditions), their engagement in actions (participation), and dialogue, with a focus on the patient (subject).enhance the perception of self-efficacy in daily activities, through the TRANSFORMATION of existing knowledge and the EMPOWERMENT of patients to take responsibility for their health and the risks they may face.

The educational model is based on individuals' knowledge (habits, roles, living conditions), their involvement in actions (participation), and dialogue, with a focus on the patient (subject).

This activity should be led by properly trained healthcare professionals who will accompany the group throughout the 12-week intervention. The professional, referred to here as a facilitator, may be a physician, physical therapist, social worker, psychologist, dietitian, or occupational therapist, and should possess strong communication skills and use language appropriate for laypeople.

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The use of audiovisual materials is optional and acts only as a supplement during the sessions. Standardised visual presentation materials (printed cards) will be provided in advance. There will be 12 sessions, each lasting 30 minutes. The aim is to promote group discussions with older adults to explore their beliefs and attitudes about falls, as well as the main barriers or limitations to implementing preventive strategies.

Meetings should always conclude by reinforcing the day's main message.

12-week agenda for the sessions/meetings:

Week	Topic
1	Introduction to the Fall Prevention Program
2	Why do older adults fall? Is falling normal in old age?
3	The importance of exercise for strengthening muscles, improving balance, and ensuring safe walking
4	What is risky behavior? Is it normal to be afraid of falling? What tasks and activities do I need to modify or avoid to prevent a fall?
5	Medications and falls
6	Is my home safe?
7	How can I take good care of my feet? What makes shoes safe?
8	Does my diet affect my risk of falling? How can I eat well?
9	How are my memory and attention? What can I do to improve them?
10	Am I seeing well ? How important is my vision to my mobility inside and outside the home?
11	Osteoporosis and fracture risk. How to get up after a fall
12	Why should I continue doing the exercises?

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At the beginning of the session, participants should be seated in a way that promotes interaction with the group members and the facilitator—suggestion: in a circle.

The facilitator's main objectives are:

- To guide the discussion towards the objectives of each session;
- To follow the minimum agenda;
- To manage the time;
- To answer questions;
- To employ strategies that encourage participation among the elderly, by suggesting scenarios and making proposals.

Evaluate each session and review information from previous sessions, maintaining a common focus on changing risky behaviors, empowering older adults to cope with everyday situations—especially those related to mobility—and improving self-efficacy to prevent falls. At the end of each session, the facilitator should take attendance and record it on the sheet provided at the end of this guide. If deemed necessary, the facilitator may also make notes relevant to the session, such as whether any objectives were not met and why.

WEEK 1

Introduction to the Fall Prevention Program

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

- 1. Explain why they are participating in the program;
- 2. Explain how the program works;
- 3. Motivate them to participate in the program.

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- At this first meeting, the seniors arrive with expectations and questions (the professional should be attentive to the experiences that arise, without, however, distracting the group);
- The professional should emphasise, at this first meeting, the importance of attending in the coming weeks;
- “Today is our first meeting! Welcome”
- The professional should introduce themselves and ask everyone else to do the same (when the seniors introduce themselves, the professional should repeat the patient’s name aloud so that everyone can hear).
- The facilitator should begin the discussion by introducing four topics:
- For this initial meeting, we will work through four questions. Let’s begin with the first one: I want everyone to follow along.
The facilitator poses the first question:
Let’s answer our first question: ‘Is falling normal in old age?’
- After asking the question, wait for the responses from the seniors and engage with the experiences that emerge from the group. Encourage them to share their own experiences of falling—how they fell, what they were doing—and this will help contextualise each person’s experience within the group.
- Ensure the session stays within the time limit and do not let any participant dominate the discussion. Give everyone present an opportunity to speak.
- The facilitator should be aware of how older adults perceive “falls” and continuously aim to dispel the myth that falling is a normal part of ageing. They should emphasise that a fall could indicate a problem with their health.

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- Next, the facilitator begins the discussion of the second question:
 - Let's move on to the second question: "Why is it important to prevent falls?"

After asking the question, wait for the older adults to respond and work with the experiences that emerge from the group.

Emphasise that a fall can be a traumatic event for older adults due to its consequences, but that it can be PREVENTED—and that is why they are here.

Points to keep in mind (if participants do not bring them up, the facilitator should find an opportunity to introduce this information):

Many older adults fall each year;

- Half of those who fall suffer serious injuries, such as fractures;
- Falls are a major cause of hospitalisation and death among older adults.

- Next, the facilitator begins the discussion of the third question:

Let's move on to the fourth question:

- "How does the program work?"

The facilitator should provide the time and location of the weekly meetings.

Please note that there are 12 weekly meetings (over 3 months) and that it is very important for each senior to attend.

ENCOURAGE PARTICIPATION. Please note that seniors can benefit from following the recommendations.

- Explain what the routine will be like within the program: educational sessions (1 hour), followed by exercises (1.5 hours) and medical follow-up if necessary.
- "Our sessions will have two important parts: an educational part (like the one we're doing now) and an exercise training part for fall prevention."
- Explain the importance of each part, trying to address any questions that arise:
- Why have Educational Sessions?
 - "Learning is important at any age, and every week we'll share important information on fall prevention."
 - "Each week we'll have a theme, and all of them are equally important for fall prevention."
 - Talk generally about the topics that will be covered: fear of falling, home safety, foot care, and footwear...
 - Pay attention to the seniors' responses and encourage weekly attendance, as this will lead to better results.

Why Exercise?

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“Every week, after the meetings, we will do exercises led by the physical therapy team or physical education teachers.”

These are exercises for body balance and muscle strength.

“Does anyone know why these exercises are recommended?”

- Wait for the participants to respond. Repeat each answer aloud so everyone in the room can hear.
- Reinforce the importance of the exercises, as the results will depend on each person’s commitment.
- Emphasise that these exercises are important for their daily lives, not only to prevent falls but also to ensure functional independence.
- Next, discuss safety precautions during the exercises, as well as appropriate clothing and nutrition:
 - “What precautions should a person take when doing exercises?” (wait for answers).
 - “How do you think a person should dress?”
 - “What do you think their diet should be like?”

Reminder:

- . Proper footwear
- . Comfortable clothing
- . Do not exercise on an empty stomach or immediately after meals.

Next, move on to the fourth question: **“What are the rules?”**

- Explain why it is important to follow the rules: punctuality, respect for any difficulties another participant may have, and the importance of asking questions (about the exercises and the meetings).

Finally, the Facilitator should encourage participants to discuss any outstanding issues in an orderly manner and promote attendance at future meetings and adherence to the recommendations. The Facilitator should emphasise the importance of properly filling out **the fall log/diaries** and reiterate the significance of completing the exercises and attending the meetings. Address any questions and share experiences raised by the group.

WEEK 2

Why do older adults fall? Is falling normal in old age?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Discuss with older adults the fact that falling is common, but not normal in old age;
2. Explain why older adults fall.

GENERAL GUIDELINES

This session will address the following important questions:

- Who falls most often and why?
- Where do older adults fall most often?
- What causes older adults to fall?
- What are the consequences of a fall for older adults?

Start with the first question: “Which groups fall most often, and why?”

The facilitator should address the three groups that fall most often:

- o Children
- o Players and athletes
- o Older people

Note: Wait for participants to respond; if none do, the facilitator should explain.

- The facilitator should address the differences among the three groups: Explain the differences in the type of fall, the manner of falling, and the reasons why older adults, children, and athletes fall. Point out that older adults fall during everyday activities.

Next, the facilitator poses the question: “When older adults fall, do they get hurt more than younger people? Why?”

Wait for the answers, and then emphasise that yes, older adults suffer more serious consequences than younger people when they fall. Explain why the consequences are more severe:

- Older adults generally have more health conditions. Many older adults may have osteoporosis, which increases their risk of bone fractures. Older adults also take longer to react when they are about to fall (longer reaction time).
- Older adults have thinner skin, so they bruise and get scrapes or cuts more easily.

Next, the facilitator should introduce the following discussion: “Falling is very dangerous. Why?”

Encourage participants to share what they know.

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Shortly after, the facilitator begins a discussion about one of the less obvious consequences: the fear of falling, a loss of self-confidence, and a decrease in physical activity.

- Discuss with the group based on their own experiences and those of people they know.
- Explain the vicious cycle: falling, fearing further falls, moving less, and thus worsening the decline in strength and balance—which are crucial for preventing falls.

Next, the facilitator should pose the following question: “What causes us to fall?”

Encourage the older adults participating to mention all the causes they can think of and discuss each one, highlighting the importance of eliminating them from our daily lives to prevent falls.

The Facilitator should keep in mind the most important causes (risk factors) and, as much as possible—and if the participants do not mention them—bring them up for discussion.

List of risk factors

- o Gait and balance disorders;
- o Poor physical fitness;
- o Muscle weakness in the lower limbs;
- o Inactivity / Immobility;
- o Decreased visual acuity;
- o Foot abnormalities / Inappropriate footwear;
- o Lack of attention / Lack of concentration;
- o Certain medical conditions: Depression, stroke, Parkinson’s disease, osteoarthritis (hips and knees), urinary incontinence. Explain why, for example, the urge to use the restroom and the fear of not making it in time. This leads to walking faster and with less attention. They may trip along the way or lose their balance more easily;
- o Polypharmacy (use of many medications) – explain that medications interact with each other and the result may not be good;
- o Incorrect medications and lack of medical guidance (emphasise the need to always inform the doctor about new medications being used);
- o Psychotropic drugs: antidepressants (medications for sadness and anxiety)

WEEK 3

The importance of exercise for strengthening muscles, improving balance, and ensuring safe walking

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Discuss the importance of physical exercise;
2. Explain why exercise can help prevent falls.

GENERAL GUIDELINES

This session will address some important questions, such as:

- o Why should we exercise?
 - o Are decreased strength and poor balance normal?
 - o Do we need strong muscles?
 - o Does having good balance prevent falls?
 - o Can physical exercise help reduce the number of falls? Why?
- The Facilitator should inquire about the purposes of physical exercise and encourage participants to identify the general benefits. Points to remember; if participants do not recall them, the facilitator should find a way to remind them:
 - o Weight loss;
 - o Muscle gain;
 - o Sense of well-being;
 - o Improved sleep and appetite;
 - o Increased energy;
 - o Improved physical fitness.

The facilitator should explain that a decrease in muscle mass (sarcopenia) and changes in balance are part of the ageing process; however, when these losses are significant and lead to reduced functionality and an increased risk of falls, it is necessary to seek help.

It should be noted that, with regular exercise, these changes are less pronounced. The facilitator should explain to older adults that muscle strength is important for:

- Performing daily activities;
- Balance recovery responses (ankle, hip, and gait strategies);
- Navigating obstacles (on the street and at home);

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- Changes in posture (e.g., standing up from a chair, sitting down, lying down, etc.).

The facilitator should explore older adults' perceptions of body balance, the risk of falls, situations involving balance deficits, and everyday situations that disrupt balance (such as walking on uneven ground, going up and down stairs and ramps, walking on the street, etc.).

- Explain that balance depends on several systems: visual, vestibular, and proprioceptive. Give examples.
- Emphasise, once again, the importance of exercises for improving body balance.

WEEK 4

What is risky behaviour? Is it common to fear falling? Which tasks and activities should I modify or avoid to prevent a fall?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Discuss the fear of falling.

GENERAL GUIDELINES

- Encourage the sharing of experiences related to the topic and introduce a discussion about fear to the group:
 - o Why do we need to discuss fear?
 - o What is fear, and what are its functions?
 - o Discuss the function of fear, highlighting both positive and negative aspects.
 - o Discuss the emotional consequences of fear:
 - Fear can protect;
 - Fear can restrict;
 - Fear can lead to isolation, loneliness, or depression.

After discussing fear in general, the facilitator should address the fear of falling.

NOTE: If, during the discussion on fear, participants spontaneously raise issues related to the fear of falling.

The facilitator might ask the following question: “Since you’ve shared these experiences about the fear of falling, what do you think? Is it normal to be afraid of falling?”

Discuss with the group specific issues related to the fear of falling and patients’ experiences:

What are the main fears associated with falls?

- o Fear of falling again—fear because they have fallen before?
- o What are the emotional causes of falls? (Remember: low self-esteem, restricted activities, isolation).
- o What are the common feelings of those who fall? (remember: guilt, shame, insecurity).

The Facilitator should address issues related to ageing and fear of falling based on participants’ experiences. How can the ageing process influence the fear of falling?

Points to discuss:

- People are different, so they have different perceptions of fear or concern about the possibility of falling;

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- Physical, mental, and social changes vary from person to person;
- Some may feel a greater sense of helplessness in the face of the changes associated with ageing and may feel more vulnerable;

Next, the facilitator should introduce a discussion on “Risk Behaviors.”

Address the patients’ own experiences:

- o Identify situations involving potential falls;
- o Review previous fall incidents;
- o What could have been done to prevent them?;
- o Discuss the importance of physical activity (exercises at home);
- o Focus on behaviors: climbing onto chairs, removing rugs, wearing slippers, etc.;
- o Recall other factors that contribute: personality and emotional changes (such as anxiety) and cognitive changes (attention problems);
- o Work with participants on anxiety: how impulsivity and low frustration tolerance contribute to falls;
- o Discuss depression: demotivation, lack of interest, medications, impaired attention, loneliness, memory;

- Next, the Facilitator should address the importance of body awareness, working on the following issues:
 - Adapting the environment: gathering suggestions and changes;
 - Identifying responsibilities and how much each person feels responsible for the fall;
 - Ability to seek and accept help;
 - Different ways of approaching aging;
 - The importance of recognizing one’s own limits and physical changes over time.
- The Facilitator should address the importance of maintaining, as best as possible, a safe home to improve mobility and accessibility.

WEEK 5

Use of medications and Falls

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Discuss whether medications can cause falls in older adults.
2. Discuss ways to avoid medication side effects.
3. Discuss which medications are more likely to lead to falls.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

This session addresses whether medications can cause falls, whether there is anything that can be done to avoid side effects, and which medications most commonly lead to falls. The facilitator should explain that medications are beneficial when used correctly, but when used incorrectly, they can indeed increase fall risk.

The facilitator should:

- explore examples from the group and emphasise that some medications, especially benzodiazepines, may impair balance, vision, attention, and orientation and therefore raise the risk of falls.
- encourage participants to discuss practical recommendations such as using a pill organiser, taking medications at the correct time, not stopping medications without advice, not mixing alcohol and medications, not taking medications without consulting a doctor, and discarding expired medicines.

Additional points include knowing which medications one takes and why, keeping an updated list in an accessible place, discussing side effects and falls with a physician, avoiding dose changes without advice, avoiding medications recommended by other people, and remembering that alcohol itself also increases fall risk.

The professional may ask HOW medications cause older adults to fall and try to gather the group's experiences on this topic.

It is important to note that some medications (MAINLY BENZODIAZEPINES, commonly known as black-label drugs), when used improperly, can affect balance, vision, and attention, leaving the elderly person disoriented and, as a result, increasing the risk of falls.

For the other two questions ("Is there anything we can do to prevent side effects, the negative effects of medication?" and "Do you know which medications are most likely to cause falls?"), the facilitator should encourage everyone to participate in the discussion and review the examples each person shares with the group, taking the opportunity to emphasize some important recommendations:

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- o Use a “pill organizer” or “medication organizer”;
- o Take your medications at the right time;
- o Don't stop taking your medications, even if you're feeling better!;
- o Don't mix medications with alcohol;
- o Don't take medications without talking to your doctor! Medications can interact with each other;
- o Older adults are more sensitive; the dose may need to be lower;
 - Throw away expired medications!

WEEK 6

Is my home safe?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Discuss the importance of the environment (on-site and at home) for falls.
2. Discuss the issue of home safety.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

- Discuss with the group that most falls occur inside the house, or nearby, and during usual activities
- Four questions will be answered:
 - What can make you fall at home?
 - Are there behaviors that can increase my risk of falling?
 - Is my home safe?
 - How can I make my house even safer?
- The Facilitator should ask about environmental risks inside the participants' homes and wait for examples. If none arise, do not fail to comment on the following items:
 - Slippery or tripping rugs (especially in high-traffic areas)
 - Poor lighting
 - Dangerous stairs: lack of handrails and difficulty seeing the edge of the step
 - Slippery / wet floors
 - Objects stored in very high cabinets and shelves
 - Furniture and objects in walkways (e.g., toys, cords, shoes)
 - Bathroom with slippery or tripping rugs, lack of non-slip mats in the shower, and no safe place to hold onto during bathing
 - Loose wires on the floor / loose floorboards
 - Pets
- For the other two questions (**“Are there behaviors that can increase my risk of falling?”**), the Facilitator should ask the question and wait for the group's experience, drawing the elderly person's attention to certain behaviors that increase the risk of falling, such as, for example: climbing on benches, chairs, small steps, placing objects too high above the head (which makes them hard to reach), talking on the cell phone while walking, wearing inappropriate shoes, among others.

It is important to highlight that changing behavior can be the first step to prevent new falls.

Other situations that should be remembered regarding risky behavior:

- Haste makes waste and falls too! Do not run, walk safely;

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- If necessary, use canes or other walking assistive devices;
- Do not hesitate to ask for help for personal safety: to cross the street, hold a bag, or get on and off the bus.

For the third question ('Is my house safe?'), the Facilitator should pose the question to the group and check if, based on what has been discussed so far, they think each person's house is safe. If appropriate, the professional may ask an older adult to share their experience as an illustrative example.

- Encourage older adults to share their experiences, but keep the conversation focused on the main topic.
- Emphasize how important it is to always keep the home organized and tidy
- Remind everyone that staying safe outside the house is just as essential
- The Facilitator can also share some safety tips to make the environment safer in case of a fall:

Always keep a list of emergency phone numbers within reach (make sure the list is easy to see, using large print)

- The Facilitator should remind the group that "safe habits" are just as important as a "safe house." Even if the house is well-prepared, risky behaviors can still lead to falls.
- Talk about simple resources that make rooms safer, such as: rubber mats for the bathroom, grab bars in the shower, and handrails on the stairs.
- The Facilitator should remind the group that safety outdoors matters too. We cannot fix a broken sidewalk or a steep curb, but we can choose where to walk and how to move around obstacles safely
- Discuss how being more cautious can prevent accidents, especially on rainy days, in crowded places, or in high-risk areas.
- Explain that falls happen more often on public transport (buses and subways). If possible:
 - Avoid traveling during "rush hours."
 - Tell the bus driver as soon as you get on that you have fallen before and ask for patience when it is time to get off (it's better to deal with a grumpy face than to suffer a fall!).
 - In the subway, try to use regular stairs or the elevator instead of escalators.

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WEEK 7

How to take good care of my feet? Is my footwear safe?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Discuss how wearing the wrong shoes can increase the risk of falling;
2. Learn how to identify unsafe footwear;
3. Talk about why taking good care of your feet is essential for maintaining your balance;
4. Encourage making small changes in daily habits to stay safe.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

The Facilitator should ask the participants how their feet are feeling . * If possible, ask them to take off their shoes and socks to look closely at their own feet. Encourage them to check for things like: Pressure points or red spots, swelling (edema) or pain, dryness, cracks (fissures), or if the skin needs moisturizing, calluses or ingrown toenails, minor deformities, like bunions or toe alignment.

Then, ask the group: **WHAT ARE OUR FEET FOR?**

- Discuss the functions of the feet: they are the body's base of support, they provide information about the body's contact with the ground, and they help propel the body forward when walking
- Ask everyone to MOVE THEIR OWN FEET.

CONCLUDE THAT, FOR ALL OF THIS TO WORK, IT IS IMPORTANT TO TAKE GOOD CARE OF YOUR FEET SO THAT THE ENTIRE BODY CAN MOVE PROPERLY AND HARMONIOUSLY.

Next, the Facilitator should ask the group about the best type of footwear for their feet:

Note: You can use the participants' own shoes as real-life examples to discuss whether they are appropriate or not for reducing the risk of falling

- Ask everyone if they believe their current shoes are appropriate;
- If they say yes, ask which features they consider appropriate for a shoe;
- If they say no, ask what flaws or problems they find in their shoes;
- Ask the participants to point out a shoe they consider safe and talk about its good features.

Features that make a shoe good and safe:

- It should be lightweight and have few seam;
- The material should be breathable (not make the feet too hot);
- It must be the right size for your feet (avoid shoes with pointed toes);
- It should stay firmly on the foot; avoid flip-flops, clogs, or loose sandals. When we wear these, we have to worry about two things at once: keeping the shoe on and taking a step;

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- It should be easy to put on, tie, or fasten;
- It should have a low heel, such as a "wedge" or "platform" style, or a block heel;
- Avoid high heels or thin "stiletto" heels.

Next, ask what the main problems with our feet are and how they relate to factors that can affect balance

After discussing the feet and their functions, the Facilitator should introduce new questions: **HOW DO YOU WALK WHEN YOU ARE IN PAIN? WHEN YOU FEEL PAIN, WHAT HAPPENS TO YOUR BALANCE?**

Note: If possible, mimic how a person's gait (way of walking) changes when they feel pain. Show how it leads to improper weight transfer and poor posture caused by the pain, which puts too much pressure on the other leg

Next, the Facilitator should ask: **What care is necessary to prevent foot pain from appearing?**

Wait for examples to emerge during the group discussion

There are some important topics to be discussed; if they do not come up naturally in the group, the Facilitator should introduce them for discussion:

- Appropriate footwear;
- New shoes: you must pay extra attention when wearing them;
- Old shoes: check for wear patterns and deformities in the footwear;
- Proper nail trimming (how to do it?);
- Proper foot hygiene, including drying between the toes;
- Moisturizing (be careful not to leave moisture between the toes);
- Special care for people with diabetes due to changes in sensitivity;
- ALWAYS observe and check your feet;
- See a podiatrist if necessary.

Another important recommendation:

- Avoid walking around the house only in socks: you could SLIP and FALL!
- To finish, reinforce the idea of WHAT THE BEST FOOTWEAR IS.

Next, the Facilitator should lead the following discussion: **“What if balance is impaired?” “What helps to prevent a fall?”**

- Wait for the group's responses, but if it does not come up naturally, find an opportunity to introduce the topic of walking aids.
- Remember that older adults often show great resistance to using them: Canes, walkers, or support from another person
- Remind them of the advantages of using these aids, such as maintaining independence (functionality) and having greater mobility in different environments
- Discuss how to use a cane: proper prescription and correct usage
- Demonstrate the correct way to use these walking aids to avoid injury or falls.

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- **Important:** The Facilitator should comment on the various uses of a cane (if these points do not come up naturally from the participants):
- **Rehabilitation** (recovery from an illness or surgery);
- **Functional training**, such as for those with visual impairments;
- **Recovery** from sprains, fractures, and other injuries;
- **Balance** (to maintain autonomy and independence);
- **PREVENTING FALLS.**

Finally, the Facilitator can ask everyone to notice how their feet feel inside their shoes—paying attention once more to their position and comfort—re-evaluating their own footwear with "new eyes."

Figure 1. Ideal Footwear

Figure 2. Inappropriate Footwear

WEEK 8

“Does diet affect my risk of falling? How can I eat well?”

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

- Try to explain that a healthy diet is related to good health conditions and, consequently, contributes to the prevention of falls.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

- The facilitator should ask whether the older adults have ever thought about the relationship between diet and falls.
- Wait for the group's response and make it clear that poor nutrition can increase the risk of falling
- The facilitator should discuss what they know about healthy eating, what they understand by it, and ask them to give examples.
- Encourage group participation while avoiding going off topic.
- Next, ask if they know someone who is inactive all the time, a sedentary person.
 - o If they do, ask whether they think this is an example that should be followed.

The objective is to reinforce the need for a healthy diet to go hand in hand with physical activity. It is necessary to stay active to prevent excessive weight gain.

Next, the facilitator should address the importance of water for health and for the prevention of falls. Ask whether it is important to drink water and wait for the response. Encourage participation and use examples that arise from the group.

Ask:

- Whether participants have any difficulty drinking fluids;
- Whether participants consume a sufficient amount of fluids;
- Whether they have ever paid attention to the amount (volume) they drink daily.

Comment on the decrease in the sensation of thirst with aging. Present options to replace water if any participant mentions that they do not like drinking water.

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Next, the facilitator should introduce the role of proteins for health and for the prevention of falls. Ask whether they know what proteins are and what they are for. Explain if the group does not know. Ask whether proteins are related to falls.

Ask if they know what proteins are and what they are for. Explain if the group is unsure.

Ask if proteins have a connection to falls.

Explain how muscles are formed and why they are important to ensure the strength needed for walking

Discuss the importance of exercises for muscle strengthening as one of the key factors in preventing falls

- Next, the Facilitator should introduce a discussion on the importance of milk and Vitamin D for general health and fall prevention.

Ask if they know why milk is important for older adults (it is a source of calcium)

Then, comment on the importance of Vitamin D for maintaining muscles and bones, and ask if it is related to falls.

Explain based on the participants' answers.

- If possible, discuss osteoporosis, including it as a risk factor for falls with serious consequences (such as fractures).

Explain how bones are formed and how they are strengthened through exercise.

- End the meeting by encouraging the older adults to practice healthy and creative eating, which is linked to aging well.

- **AND HIGHLIGHT THAT EATING WELL IS AN ART!**

WEEK 9

How would you assess my memory and cognitive focus? What steps can I take for improvement?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. Defining memory;
2. Defining attention;
3. Memory and attention in the context of aging;
4. Methods for enhancing memory and focus.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

For the first question, the Facilitator should lead a discussion on what memory is, focusing on the following concepts:

- A repository of information received throughout our lives that we are able to access (recall);
- The entire process also depends on other bodily functions:
 - Senses (Vision / Hearing / Touch / Taste / Smell);
 - Emotions and Thoughts;
- Memory allows us to:
 - Know who we are and who others are;
 - Recognize places and people;
 - Perform tasks we have learned;
 - Develop new skills.

For the second question, the Facilitator should discuss the following aspects of attention, always creating space for participation from the elderly:

- The capacity to focus on and select stimuli, establishing relationships between them.
- Three basic factors are required for attention to function:
 - Physiological Factor: Neurological conditions and the context in which the individual is situated;
 - Motivational Factor: Depends on how the stimulus is presented and how it sparks interest;
 - Concentration: Depends on the intensity and demand of the stimulus, leading to better focus on the stimulus source.
- Note that memory is closely related to attention; in many cases, forgetfulness is caused by a lack of attention rather than a memory problem itself.
- Keep in mind clinical conditions that interfere with these factors, such as depression, anxiety, medications, etc.

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Next, the Facilitator should introduce the next question: **"What happens to our memory and attention as we get older?"**

The Facilitator will explain the natural changes that happen to our memory with age:

- **Less focus:** It becomes harder to pay close attention.
- **Slower recall:** It takes a little longer to "find" and pull out information we know.
- **Short-term memory:** It's harder to hold onto brand-new information for a long time.

Next, the Facilitator should talk about **"divided attention"** and ask the group: **"Why does doing two things at the same time increase the risk of a fall?"**

- Explain that, compared to younger people, older adults find it harder to focus on more than one thing at once.
- When this happens, we tend to move more slowly, take shorter steps, and may not notice obstacles in our way.
- Because our reaction time is also slower, we are more likely to make mistakes.

Ask the group: **"Has anyone here ever fallen while trying to do more than one thing at the same time?"**

If no one has a story to share, give some common examples:

- Walking on uneven ground while having a conversation.
- Carrying shopping bags while trying to step onto a bus.
- Looking for keys in a purse while walking down the stairs.

Reinforce how important paying attention is for preventing falls, using the examples discussed above.

WEEK 10

Can I see clearly? How important is my vision for moving around safely, both inside and outside my home?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. **Talk about** how our eyesight naturally changes as we get older.
2. **Clarify** that "weak eyesight" isn't always just part of aging—it could be a medical condition that needs treatment.
3. **Explain** that not being able to see clearly increases the risk of tripping or falling.
4. **Discuss** the practical steps we can take to improve our vision and keep our eyes healthy.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

- The Facilitator will start the session by leading a discussion to answer the following:
 - **Why is it so important to have good eyesight?**
 - **Is there a link between our vision and falling?**
 - **Does "weak eyesight" increase my chance of a fall?** (Here, the facilitator should emphasize how seeing well helps us keep our balance).
- Next, the Facilitator will ask the group: "**Is it true that every older person will eventually have 'weak eyesight'?**"
- The **Facilitator** should discuss the following changes in vision that can happen as we age:
 - **Blurry vision:** Finding it harder to see fine details or notice things clearly.
 - **Difficulty seeing contrast:** For example, it becomes harder to tell the difference between the sidewalk and the street, or to see the edge of a step on the stairs.
 - **Slower adjustment to the dark:** It takes the eyes longer to get used to a room when the lights go out.
 - **Poor depth perception:** Finding it harder to judge how far away things are or how deep a step is.

At the end, remind the group that **these changes are not always a normal part of aging.**

- Next, the Facilitator should ask the group: "**Do you know of any illnesses or conditions that can make your eyesight worse?**"

The Facilitator should highlight the following:

- **"Weak eyesight" can be a sign of a disease:** Some conditions start this way, such as cataracts, glaucoma, macular degeneration, and vision problems caused by diabetes or high blood pressure;
- **These conditions** are more common as we get older;
- **Comparing Normal Vision and Cataracts:** Explain what it's like to live with a cataract: **What is it?** The lens inside the eye becomes cloudy (like a "fogged-up" window), which makes it very hard to see clearly. **What does it feel like?** At first, it's like looking through dirty glasses or a light mist. As it gets worse, the person may only be able to see blurry shapes or shadows;
- Discuss how this blurry vision makes daily activities harder and, most importantly, how it **affects your balance**. If you can't see the ground clearly, it's much easier to trip;
- Reassure the group about the treatment:
 - **Don't be afraid of the surgery:** The results are excellent, and the recovery is very quick.
 - **A safer life:** Fixing your vision is one of the best ways to **reduce your risk of falling**.
- Next, the Facilitator should ask the group: **"What can I do to improve my vision?"**
 - The first step is to **see an Ophthalmologist** (an eye doctor)
 - Once again, ask the participants why they think this check-up is important. Make sure to cover these key points:
 - **Updating your prescription:** Getting the right "strength" for your glasses helps you see clearly and lowers your risk of falling.
 - **Checking for eye diseases:** Mention conditions like cataracts, glaucoma, macular degeneration, and vision issues caused by diabetes or high blood pressure. (Encourage the group to try and remember these names!)
 - **Exploring treatments:** Discuss how treatments—like new glasses, surgeries, or medications—can help you see better and, as a result, keep you safer from falls.

Useful Tips for Every Day:

- **Wear your glasses all the time!** This includes while you are inside your home.
- **Brighten up your home:** Always keep your rooms and hallways well-lit so you can see where you are walking.

Next, the Facilitator should have a short talk about glasses, covering the following points:

Types of Glasses (Single Vision vs. Multifocal): Talk about the disadvantages of multifocal or bifocal lenses that have a very sharp change between seeing far away and seeing up close. These lenses can make it harder to judge distances or see the ground

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clearly. This can affect an older person's balance because their eyes struggle to adjust to the depth.

Multifocal glasses are very handy because they correct your vision for both "far away" and "close up" in the same pair. Research shows that people who wear multifocal glasses have a **higher risk of falling** when they are outside the house or walking up and down stairs.

Normal

Cataract

Normal

Retinopathy

Normal

Glaucoma

WEEK 11

Osteoporosis and the Risk of Breaking a Bone.

How to Get Up After a Fall.

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. **Explain** what osteoporosis is and what causes it.
2. **Discuss** who is most at risk and how likely they are to develop it.
3. **Talk about** the best ways to prevent osteoporosis and keep bones strong.
4. **Demonstrate** exactly how to get back up safely after a fall.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

- The Facilitator should start by asking the group if they know what osteoporosis is, if anyone has been diagnosed with it, and if they are currently following any treatment.

Use this moment to discuss why this condition is so important when we talk about falls.

STRESS THIS POINT THROUGHOUT THE DISCUSSION: The main goal of learning about this topic is to **prevent falls and avoid serious injuries.**

- Next, the **Facilitador** (Facilitator) begins a discussion on the following question: **What is osteoporosis and what causes it?** The Facilitator should aim to use simple terms, such as: “A disease that affects the bones”; “Osteoporosis means porous bone”; “the cause of osteoporosis is unknown,” among other possibilities. Investigar, se os participantes têm noção de que os principais locais de fratura são quadril, punho e coluna.

Investigate whether participants are aware that the main fracture sites are the **hip, wrist, and spine.**

- Next, the Facilitator moves on to discuss another question: **Who is at risk of having osteoporosis? And what is the risk of having osteoporosis?**

The Facilitator should encourage the participants to share their knowledge and, during the discussion, introduce the population with the highest prevalence and the risk factors (in case they are not mentioned by the seniors):

- Women;
- Family history of osteoporosis;
- Postmenopausal women;
- White people;
- Older people (advanced age);

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- Individuals with certain conditions: diabetes, hyperthyroidism, rheumatoid arthritis;
- Certain medications;
- Smokers and people who consume alcohol;
- Excessive coffee consumption;
- Sedentary lifestyle (lack of physical activity);
- The following may be added: It is a **silent disease** that generally has no symptoms—most of the time, the person does not feel that they have osteoporosis;
- The diagnosis is made through an exam called **bone densitometry**.

Next, the Facilitator introduces the third question: **How to prevent it?** The Facilitator seeks to draw out from each participant their understanding of how to prevent osteoporosis. If, during the discussion, any of the items below are not mentioned, cite them and allow the seniors to interact.

- Engage in physical exercise;
- Stop smoking;
- Decrease alcohol consumption;
- Decrease coffee intake;
- Ingest calcium (according to medical guidance);
- Review medications (according to medical guidance).

Next, the Facilitator introduces the following question: **Why is it important to prevent it?**

Highlight the importance of prevention: it avoids fractures. Emphasize how much a person's life changes when they suffer a hip (femur) fracture.

Then, propose a discussion regarding the **treatment of osteoporosis**.

Wait for the seniors to recall some treatments and, if they do not come up during the discussion, mention the following items:

- Regular physical exercise;
- Quit smoking;
- Reduce alcohol consumption;
- Ingest Calcium / Vitamin D (Healthy eating);
- Follow the doctor's recommendations.

Next, the Facilitator will introduce the topic of **how to get up after a fall**.

- **General guidelines:**
 - If you fall and feel immediate intense pain or have difficulty moving a leg or arm, **call for help**. Do not try to get up and do not let anyone else pull you up or pull you by the arm (the bone may be "partially" broken, and the movement could cause it to break completely).
 - Go to a healthcare facility so a doctor can evaluate whether or not a fracture occurred (sometimes only an X-ray can identify a fracture).

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- If you hit your head, watch for signs and symptoms such as dizziness, vomiting, or mental confusion (disorientation), which can happen immediately or some time after the fall.
- **Demonstrate how to get up after a fall.**

<http://www.salford.gov.uk/falls-after.htm>

WEEK 12

Why should I keep exercising?

OBJECTIVES OF THIS MEETING:

1. **Discuss the various benefits** that regular physical activity brings to one's health;
2. **Discuss how much** regular physical activity helps in preventing (combating) falls;
3. **Motivate the participants** to perform the home exercises they were taught, in order to maintain the functional gains achieved over the 12 weeks;
4. **Remember the importance** of practicing everything that was learned during the 12 meetings.

GENERAL GUIDELINES:

- The Facilitator should start with the following question: **Which physical exercises are important?**

Address that the most important physical exercises for preventing falls are those learned during the 12 weeks of intervention and that, from now on, it is essential for everyone to continue exercising "on their own" at home.

- The benefits will be long-lasting if you do your part. **IT IS TIME TO PUT WHAT YOU HAVE LEARNED INTO PRACTICE!**

The Facilitator should encourage a discussion regarding the benefits of continuing to practice the exercises learned during the 12-week intervention. If these benefits are not mentioned by the participants, the Facilitator should list them again so that the seniors can commit them to memory and strive to practice the exercises regularly:

- Increased muscle strength;
- Greater agility;
- Greater flexibility;
- Improved balance;
- Better coordination.

(Provide examples for each item).

- Next, the **Facilitator** should introduce the following questions:
 - **Besides exercise, what is essential for maintaining good health?**
 - **What other aspects of health are also important and were learned during these 12 weeks?**

Wait for responses and create space for group interaction, being careful to avoid losing focus.

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Allow the participants to discuss among themselves, while providing some "hints" to evoke themes discussed in previous **Educational Meetings**:

- Vision and hearing;
 - Memory and attention;
 - Healthy eating;
 - Correct use of medications – consult the doctor;
 - Medical follow-up: Osteoarthritis, Osteoporosis;
 - Appropriate footwear;
 - Home safety;
 - Risk behaviors;
 - Fear of falling.
-
- **Remind everyone** that this is the final Meeting of the program and emphasize that practicing exercises is essential for preventing falls.

 - **Thank everyone** for their participation and reinforce the need to follow the guidelines for their own benefit.

 - **Final recommendations:**
 - **ALWAYS** do the exercises and do them **REGULARLY**.
 - Remember the need to fill out the falls diary (**WEEKLY**).
 - Ask if there are any questions.